

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE IN SOLVING LINEAR SYSTEMS: SCILAB AND MICROSOFT VISUAL STUDIO IN ACTION

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Abstract - This article compares Microsoft Visual Studio and Scilab software, evaluating their efficiency and speed when executing a code. In both software packages, we used an algorithm based on the Gauss Elimination Method. After carrying out three series of tests, each with a cycle of 10 iterations, the remarkable superiority of the Scilab software became evident.

Keywords: Optimization; Comparative Analysis; Gauss Elimination Method; Visual Studio; SciLab.

1| INTRODUCTION

In various branches of engineering, many problems can be solved using systems of linear equations. One of the most common approaches to solving these equations is the Gauss elimination method.

The Gauss elimination method, also known as Gaussian elimination, is a fundamental technique in linear algebra and in solving systems of linear equations. This method involves transforming a system of equations into an upper triangular form, thus simplifying the resolution of the unknowns. Gauss elimination is widely applied in various fields, such as engineering, physics, economics and computer science, due to its effectiveness in solving complex systems of equations in a systematic and efficient way.

Both SciLab and Visual Studio are versatile tools that can be used to solve linear systems using the Gauss elimination method. SciLab, which is an open-source platform for numerical computing, offers a series of functions and libraries that simplify the implementation of Gauss elimination, making the process more accessible to engineers and scientists. On the other hand, Visual Studio, an integrated development environment (IDE), allows the creation of customized programs in languages such as C++ or C#, making it easier to implement the Gauss elimination algorithm in more specific contexts or in engineering projects that disable greater control over the code. Both tools offer resources to help solve linear systems efficiently.

For this comparison between the two softwares, their speed and efficiency were analyzed using code from the software's own tool library.

2| BUILDING THE CODE FROM THE LINEAR SYSTEM

2.1| LINEAR SYSTEM

The linear system used was generated from a set of electrical loops, where it was necessary to calculate the voltages generated from the current and its resistors.

Fig. 1. Example used in a Numerical Calculus class [A. M. Oliveira, 2023].

2.2| SCILAB CODE

The code was built in SciLab as follows:

```
1 E1= input("Valor-E1: ");
2 E2= input("Valor-E2: ");
3 E3= input("Valor-E3: ");
4 R1= input("Valor-R1: ");
5 R2= input("Valor-R2: ");
6 R3= input("Valor-R3: ");
7
8 n_iteracoes = 10; // Número de iterações desejadas
9
10 for i = 1:n_iteracoes
11     // Inicia o cronômetro para cada iteração
12     tic();
```

Fig. 2. Data entry and start of code iterations and timing [authorial, 2023].

```
13
14 a = [R1, -R2, 0; 0, R2, R3; 1, 1, -1];
15
16 b = [E1-E2; E2+E3; 0];
17
18 n = size(a,1);
19
20 x = linsolve(a,b);
21 I1=x(1)*-1;
22 I2=x(2)*-1;
23 I3=x(3)*-1;
24
25 V1=R1*I1;
26 V2=R2*I2;
27 V3=R3*I3;
28
29 disp("Matriz A");
30 disp(a);
31 disp("-----");
32 disp("Matriz B");
33 disp(b);
34 disp("-----");
35 disp("Solução por eliminação de Gauss");
36 disp("Resultados I");
37 disp(I1);
38 disp(I2);
39 disp(I3);
40 disp("-----");
41 disp("Resultados V");
42 disp(V1);
43 disp(V2);
44 disp(V3);
45 disp("-----");
46
47
48 function [x] = eliminacao_gaussiana(a, b);
49 for k = 1:n
50     for i = k+1:n
51         m = a(i,k)/a(k,k);
52         a(i,k) = 0;
53         for j = k+1:n
54             a(i,j) = a(i,j)-m*a(k,j);
55         end
56         b(i) = b(i)-m*b(k);
57     end
58 end
59 end
60
```

Fig. 3. Logical arrangement of matrices and algorithm for the Gauss elimination method [authorial, 2023].

```
60
61 tempo_decorrido = toc()*1000;
62 // Exibe o tempo decorrido para cada iteração em milissegundos
63 disp('Iteração: ' + string(1));
64 disp('Tempo de execução: ' + string(tempo_decorrido) + ' milissegundos')
65 end
66
```

Fig. 4. End of timing and code iterations [authorial, 2023].

2.3| VISUAL STUDIO CODE

The code was created in Visual Studio, using the C# programming language, as follows:

```
2 using System;
3 using System.Diagnostics;
4 using static System.Net.Mime.MediaTypeNames;
5
6 namespace ConsoleApp2
7 {
8     0 referências
9     class Program
10    {
11        0 referências
12        public static void Main(string[] args)
13        {
14
15            Console.WriteLine("Digite o valor de E1: ");
16            E1 = double.Parse(Console.ReadLine());
17            Console.WriteLine("Digite o valor de E2: ");
18            E2 = double.Parse(Console.ReadLine());
19            Console.WriteLine("Digite o valor de E3: ");
20            E3 = double.Parse(Console.ReadLine());
21            Console.WriteLine("Digite o valor de R1: ");
22            R1 = double.Parse(Console.ReadLine());
23            Console.WriteLine("Digite o valor de R2: ");
24            R2 = double.Parse(Console.ReadLine());
25            Console.WriteLine("Digite o valor de R3: ");
26            R3 = double.Parse(Console.ReadLine());
27
28            for (int i = 0; i < 10; ++i)
29            {
30                // Inicia o cronômetro
31                Stopwatch stopwatch = new Stopwatch();
32                stopwatch.Start();
33            }
34        }
35    }
36 }
37
```

Fig. 5. Data entry and start of code iterations and timing [authorial, 2023].

```
34
35
36 // for (int i = 0; i < 10; i++)
37 {
38
39     double[,] A = {{R1, -R2, 0},
40                  {0, R2, R3},
41                  {1, 1, -1}};
42
43     double[] B = { E1 - E2, E2 + E3, 0 };
44
45     double[] X = Gauss(A, B);
46
47     Console.WriteLine();
48     Console.WriteLine("Solução por eliminação de Gauss.");
49     Console.WriteLine();
50     Console.WriteLine("I1 = (0)*, X(0)");
51     Console.WriteLine("I2 = (0)*, X(1)");
52     Console.WriteLine("I3 = (0)*, X(2)");
53     Console.WriteLine();
54     Console.WriteLine("V1 = (0)*, R1 * X(0)");
55     Console.WriteLine("V2 = (0)*, R2 * X(1)");
56     Console.WriteLine("V3 = (0)*, R3 * X(2)");
57     Console.WriteLine();
58 }
59
60 static double[] Gauss(double[,] A, double[] b)
61 {
62     int n = b.Length;
63
64     // Eliminação gaussiana
65     for (int k = 0; k < n - 1; k++)
66     {
67         for (int i = k + 1; i < n; i++)
68         {
69             double factor = A[i, k] / A[k, k];
70             A[i, k] = 0.0;
71             b[i] = factor * b[k];
72             for (int j = k + 1; j < n; j++)
73             {
74                 A[i, j] -= factor * A[k, j];
75             }
76         }
77     }
78
79     // Resolução retroativa
80     for (int i = n - 1; i >= 0; i--)
81     {
82         double sum = 0.0;
83
84         for (int j = i + 1; j < n; j++)
85         {
86             sum += A[i, j] * X[j];
87         }
88         X[i] = (b[i] - sum) / A[i, i];
89     }
90
91     return X;
92 }
93
94 // Retorna b;
95
96
97
```

Fig. 6. Logical arrangement of matrices and algorithm for the Gauss elimination method [authorial, 2023].


```

180 // Para o cronômetro
181 stopwatch_stopC;
182
183 // Fim da tempo decorrido
184 TimeSua = stopwatch_getTime();
185
186 Console.WriteLine("Tempo de execução: " + i + " * tempoDecorridoMdi, TotalMilissegundos + " milissegundos");
187
188 Console.ReadLine();
189
190
191
192
193
194
195
196
197
198
199
200
    
```

Fig. 7. End of timing and code iterations [authorial, 2023].

3| RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

After a comparative analysis of the SciLab and Visual Studio software, with three series of tests, each with a cycle of 10 iterations, it was clear that the Scilab software was superior, with greater speed and less variation. The results can be seen in the tables below.

Table I - Tests Solving Linear Systems by Gauss elimination

Solving Linear Systems by Gauss elimination			Solving Linear Systems by Gauss elimination			Solving Linear Systems by Gauss elimination		
Average Time with 10 iterations - Test 1 (With computer in multitask)			Average Time with 10 iterations - Test 2 (With computer in multitask)			Average Time with 10 iterations - Test 3 (With computer in multitask)		
Index	Visual Studio C#	SciLab	Index	Visual Studio C#	SciLab	Index	Visual Studio C#	SciLab
1	5,62	1,31	1	7,04	1,47	1	5,30	1,27
2	1,34	2,10	2	2,59	4,64	2	2,45	1,39
3	1,97	2,64	3	2,58	1,24	3	3,26	0,84
4	3,26	1,42	4	2,09	1,59	4	3,24	0,58
5	1,73	0,82	5	2,18	1,45	5	2,80	0,43
6	1,48	0,59	6	1,92	1,99	6	1,75	1,09
7	0,91	0,52	7	1,93	0,77	7	2,18	0,94
8	1,19	1,58	8	2,66	1,80	8	3,14	1,16
9	2,78	2,06	9	2,80	0,90	9	2,54	1,01
10	1,75	5,46	10	1,41	0,99	10	3,38	1,15
Average time (ms)	2,21	1,85	Average time (ms)	2,72	1,68	Average time (ms)	3,00	0,99
Result (ms)	0,35	SciLab Faster	Result (ms)	1,04	SciLab Faster	Result (ms)	2,02	SciLab Faster

In conclusion, the study compared the use of SciLab and Visual Studio in implementing the Gauss elimination method to solve linear systems. The linear system under examination, derived from electrical loops, required efficient calculation of voltages. Through a comprehensive analysis, SciLab emerged as the superior choice, demonstrating higher speed and lower variation in results compared to Visual Studio. This outcome highlights SciLab's effectiveness as an open-source platform for numerical computing and its suitability for engineers and scientists tackling complex linear equation problems.

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